

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

In this technology-driven world, access to information has been made easier than ever. Continuous modifications in the interactions among individuals daily, prompted by technological progress, have significantly enhanced operational and professional efficiency. Conversation is an interesting type of interaction, solely because it bridges the gap of communication. It can occur in human-human interaction (HH) and human-computer interaction (HCI).

A chatbot is a tool that can simulate this kind of interaction by understanding the context and deliverance of an appropriate response. It is a program that simulates a conversation between a human and a computer. Chatbots are used a lot in customer interactions, marketing on social network sites, and instant messaging the client. Integrating chatbots into websites can be very profitable for business owners who are trying to reach a new audience. (Macdonald, 2019)

Entrepreneurs have realized that without a fast, multilingual customer-service team that offers 24/7 support to the customers, it will be difficult to succeed in any industry. With the integration of a chatbot into a website, this service is provided at the customer's beck and call. While chatbots cannot hold a truly natural conversation, they perform well at being consistent as they will only do what they are programmed to do.

Strutynskyi (2020) stated that chatbots cannot replace humans in sales completely, but they can take over answering repetitive questions and taking simple orders. For cases when advanced support is needed, a "Call a human agent" button is often present. With this short overview done, it is safe to say that since their first appearance, chatbots have been bringing revolutionary changes to the business world and will keep doing so.

Huang (2021) stated that artificial Intelligent machines can operate tasks of varying complexity, from general work to sophisticated operations such as object detection using computer vision. Prominent trends in this field are human brain simulation, natural-language processing and neural networking to name the least. An example of an Artificial Intelligence system is a Chatbot. A chatbot is an intelligent conversational computer program that mimics human conversation in its natural form using interactive textual or speech skills.

Since the introduction of the first of its kind, ELIZA, in 1966, chatbots have evolved with the progressive increase in computational capabilities and advances in Natural Language Processing tools and techniques. ELIZA was a landmark system that inspired further research in the field. The application of chatbots has expanded with the emergence of Deep Learning algorithms. One of the new, and the most interesting application, is the development of smart personal assistants (such as Amazon's Alexa, Apple's Siri, Google's Google Assistant (Google Developers, 2023), Microsoft's Cortana, and IBM's Watson).

Voice assistants such as Apple SIRI, Microsoft Cortana, Amazon Alexa, and Google Assistant are widely spread in today's world. These systems are continually developing thanks to breakthroughs in speech recognition and text-to-speech technologies. A major role in this development plays new research in the area of deep learning, gains in computing power of GPUs and releases of ever more powerful mobile devices.

A chatbot can process user input and produce an output. Usually, chatbots take natural language text as input, and the output should be the most relevant response to the user input sentence. Chatbots can directly converse with users using artificial intelligence and Machine Learning concepts. It can also be defined as an "online human-computer dialogue system(s) with natural language". Chatbots constitute therefore an automated dialogue system, that can attend to thousands of potential users at once. Usually, a chatbot program understands one or

more human languages although a general understanding of naturally-spoken language across multiple dialogue steps, even in single task-oriented situations still cannot be achieved.

Hence, the system interprets human language input using information fed to it from the model or the database. Creating a chatbot system for websites enables quick question response and problem-solving. This serves a great purpose in saving a lot of money and time.

1.2 Statement of Problem

Website owners face a lot of issues ranging from providing customer support to engaging and interacting with users at various points in time. Hence, businesses waste a lot of capital and time, thereby, reducing their efficiency in the business sector. There is so much a human can do when providing help. This is where a web-based chatbot system comes in. (Huang, 2021)

The chatbot system aims to replace the human personnel that should be doing this job. The system will constitute a chat CUI (Conversational User Interface) that will cater for different and varying needs per user. The system consists of a chat module that interacts with the user's input. The chatbot system can help customers find the right services and products as well as answer their questions.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

This aim of this research is to design and implement a web-based chatbot system using Python and NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) and the specific objectives are:

- (i) to process extracted data into a model using PyTorch;
- (ii) to design and implement a web-based chatbot system to interact with website users and auto-respond to user questions;
- (iii) to design a descriptive land-on webpage to host the chatbot system;
- (iv) to analyse the results of the chatbot and test if it is functional.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The use of web-based chatbots comes in handy in this generation due to easy access to mobile devices and the internet. It is a technological revolution that is impacting the user experience of many websites as it helps with easy communication. The use of AI and chatbots improve the quality of day-to-day operations. Chatbots are developed and become so popular due to the increased use of smart devices and IoT technology. MacDonald (2019) There have been several attempts at solving the problem of expanding datasets. Some authors suggest using a NLP library with a programming language like Python, some also suggest using data pre-sets to determine what response the chatbot system gives. In this work, a combination of datasets with NLP libraries is used to implement a chatbot system. Some research has been done in this area to define and prove the effectiveness of this concept and the exploration of this concept is currently ongoing. Strutynskyi (2020) Despite the amount of existing work in the area of machine learning, this concept has not yet been investigated concerning chatbots, which is the topic of this work.

A more detailed literature overview is presented in the *Literature review* section of this thesis.

1.5 Scope of the Study

(de Bayser, 2017) This work is focused majorly on helping out people who are trying to integrate a round-the-clock chatbot system in their websites, but are struggling to do so. It might also be interesting for researchers working in the area of Machine Learning, companies looking for a suitable chatbot for business applications, or students seeking further knowledge about different areas of AI.

1.6 Definition of Terms

Accuracy: The degree to which the result of a measurement, calculation and specification conforms to the correct value or standard.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): The simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. Specific applications of AI include expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognition and machine vision.

Conversational User Interface (CUI): A user interface for computers that emulates a conversation with a real human.

Data: Information in its raw form must be processed before it can become meaningful information.

Dataset: A collection of related data or information composed of separate elements which can be manipulated as a unit by a computer.

Graphical User Interface (GUI): a form of user interface that allows users to interact with electronic devices through graphical icons and audio indicators such as primary notation, instead of text-based UIs, typed command labels or text navigation.

Machine Learning (ML): An AI technique that teaches computers to learn from experience.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): The application of computational techniques to analyse and synthesise natural language and speech.

Natural Language Understanding (NLU): A subtopic of natural-language processing in artificial intelligence that deals with machine reading comprehension.

Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK): A suite of libraries and programs for symbolic and statistical natural language processing for English written in Python.

1.7 Project Layout

This project is organized as follows:

Chapter One: presents the background to the study, statement of the problem, aim and objectives of the study, significance of the study, definition of terms and project layout.

Chapter Two: contains the overview of existing work in the area of building chatbots, training them using a dialogue corpus and a description of the related concepts

Chapter Three: discusses the several techniques employed in achieving the different objectives of the study.

Chapter Four: presents the results and discussion.

Chapter Five: entails the summary, conclusion and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Chatbots

To justify the need for a new approach, the first step was to overview the existing works on building chatbots and their effectiveness. To test the method, a case study chatbot that will allow us to test this new approach was developed. Before developing the chatbot, the tech stack that was used was specified. To support this choice, the existing methods of building dialogue systems such as chatbots are overviewed.

The term “chatbot” can be defined in different ways. A chatbot is a piece of software that conducts a conversation via auditory or textual methods (Shawar and Atwell, 2007). This could be text-based, on a spoken conversation (in case of voice-based queries). Alternatively, a chatbot could be defined as a computer program that can simulate a conversation or chat with a user in natural language through messaging applications, websites, or mobile applications and interact with users according to their input and should be available 24/7.

Chatbots are used for different tasks but mostly are used for information acquisition. Chatbots are typically used in dialogue systems for various practical purposes including customer service or information acquisition. Chatbots can be accessed or run through different tech gadgets namely on local PCs and mobile phones, though most of the time it is accessed through the internet. Most Chatbots are accessed via virtual assistants such as Google Assistant and Amazon Alexa (Amazon Developer Services, 2023), via messaging apps such as Facebook Messenger or WeChat, or via individual organizations' apps and websites.

Chatbots can be classified into usage categories such as conversational commerce (e-commerce via chat), analytics, communication, customer support, design, developer tools, education, entertainment, finance, food, games, health, HR, marketing, news, personal, productivity, shopping, social, sports, travel and utilities (Messenger Bot Landscape, 2017). It

can be compelling, captivating and spell-binding. It is a conversational agent which interacts with users in a certain domain or on a particular topic with input in natural language sentences. Mainly a chatbot works by a user asking some questions or initiating different topics of discussion, where the chatbot answers questions with preferred information. Some chatbots use sophisticated natural language processing systems, but many simpler ones scan for keywords within the input, then pull a reply with the most matching keywords, or the most similar wording pattern, from a database. Chatbots can be referred to as software agents that pretend as human entities. These are the agents with Artificial Intelligence embedded and using Natural Language Processing they can answer user questions. A predefined knowledge base helps develop a response to the query. The mobile Chatbot system comprises various parts which allow the person to create an account and get access to the system. There are different databases used, for storing the information. The system is Artificial Intelligence powered using a trained model using PyTorch and a manually done dataset for questions related to every aspect of the website. The chatbot system is created using Microsoft Visual Studio Code using Python, Flask and HTML (HyperText Markup Language) & CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), JavaScript for User Interface designing. This model is hosted on the website, and responses fed are stored in a JSON file. (Adiwardana, 2020)

A Chatbot can further be defined as a computer program which responds like an intelligent entity when conversed with using either a mobile or desktop. There is barely any Artificial Intelligence Chatbot designed for websites that are designed from scratch but there are well-known Chatbot frameworks that incorporate ALICE (Shawar and Atwell, 2007), SimSimi, or Cleverbot. The vast majority of them are online, however, there remain solitary Chatbot frameworks like Artificial Intelligence Bliss and Kari. In chatbot systems that utilise Natural Language Processing as the calculation, the chatbot attempts to comprehend the importance of the characteristic dialect that is inputted. The information would then be parsed to get the

sentence structure (i.e., thing, descriptor, and so on...) of the information. At that point, the parsed info is handled to get the importance of the sentence.

While this might be a decent methodology of how a chatbot ought to do, this methodology would influence the chatbot to answer an undeniable inquiry dependent on how huge the learning of the chatbot system is.

2.2 Types of Chatbots

Three types of Chatbots

Menu-Based Chatbots: These are the most basic type of chatbots on the market today.

These chatbots require the user to make several selections to dig deeper towards the ultimate answer. While these chatbots are sufficient for answering that handful of basic questions that make up 80% of support queries; they fall well short in more advanced scenarios in which there are too many variables or too much knowledge at play to predict how users should get to specific answers with confidence (Goboomtown, 2018).

Keyword-Based Chatbots: These types of chatbots can listen to what users type and respond appropriately. These chatbots utilize customizable keywords to determine how to serve an appropriate response to the user. These types of chatbots fall short when they have to answer a lot of similar questions. The bots will start slipping when keyword redundancies exist between several questions (Goboomtown, 2018). It is becoming quite popular to see chatbots that are a hybrid of keyword-based and menu-based. These bots provide users with the choice to try to ask their questions directly or use the bot's menu if the keyword functionality is yielding poor results.

Contextual Chatbots: Goboomtown (2018) Contextual chatbots are by far the most advanced of the three bots discussed in this post. These bots utilize Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to remember conversations with specific users to learn and grow over time. Unlike keyword-based chatbots, contextual chatbots are smart enough to

self-improve based on what users are asking for and how they are asking it (Garcia, 2023). For example, a contextual chatbot that allows users to order pizza will store the data from each conversation and learn what the user likes to order. The result is that eventually when a user chats with this bot, it will remember their most common order, their delivery address, and their payment information and simply ask if they'd like to repeat this order. Instead of having to respond to several questions the user just has to answer with 'Yes' and pizza is on its way!"

2.3 How Do Chatbots Work?

Briefly and as mentioned in the definition, humans interact with chatbots. There are two ways to interact with a chatbot:

- i. **Text:** The chatbot analyses the inputted text and matches the text with predefined data called intents which are categorized to manage the conversation. The user utterance is tagged with one of these intents, even if what the user says stretches over two or more intents. Most chatbots will take the intent with the highest score and take the conversation down that avenue. Rahman (2017)
- ii. **Voice:** (Rahman, 2017) Some chatbots can interact and understand the voice of the user using a set of application programming interfaces (APIS) that converts the recorded voice to the language and then convert the voice to words of that language and then deal with the transformed text as mentioned above.

2.3.1 Options to Build a Chatbot

- a. **From Scratch:** At first, the opportunities for the chatbot have to be identified and then decide its field and scope to achieve efficiency and accuracy. and a precise understanding of customer needs is required to solve operational challenges. Then the design of the bot comes to be a significant stage to decide the user engagement with

an app or a website. and thus, can categorize chatbot interactions as structured and unstructured interactions. Garcia (2023)

- a. **Structured interaction.** This is a popular kind of interaction. Since customer queries are known, and can be easily designed— it's just like an FAQ section of an app or a website. This information will link to contact information, services, products, etc.
- b. **Unstructured interaction.** The unstructured conversation flow includes freestyle plain text. It's hard to predict what queries will emerge and it looks like an extempore speech competition for the chatbot. the role of AI comes to light here, it decodes the context of the text based on NLP analysis. while the same NLP will provide a voice to the chatbot. The latter choice will need specialized chatbot developers with an understanding of programming languages, machine learning, and AI. Code-based frameworks can be used to build and handle the chatbot like wit.ai and api.ai
- b. **Using platforms:** It is similar to scratch chatbots but the only difference is that much expertise isn't needed to use chatbot builder platforms like Chatfuel, Botsify and Rasa, it's not hard or impossible to achieve it. but it's not possible to create an NLP-enabled chatbot that can deal with unstructured data (White, 2019) (Lee, 2020).

2.3.2 Chatbot Platforms Alternatives

- a. **IBM Watson:** is touted as a question-and-answer system that can be used to build applications and chatbots. The IBM Watson platform allows the creation of an application that shares a dialogue interaction between the chatbot and users on Quick n' Easy Projector Rentals. The IBM interface is simple to use, and no back-end

coding is shown at first glance. The chatbot can be easily integrated into other applications such as Slack, Facebook, and Twilio (Smith, 2022).

- b. **Google Dialogflow:** is an easy-to-understand conversational agent. Theoretically, a chatbot can be up and running by understanding 3 core concepts: intents, entities, and dialogue control. As stated earlier, these general concepts are followed across a majority of the chatbot platforms that have been mentioned.
- c. **Rasa:** is an open-source chatbot that is equipped with a natural language processing tool. The open-source tool is called Rasa NLU. The machine learning algorithm that Rasa uses can be tweaked and customized till a model that provides the results desired has been made. Rasa NLU can be run wherever it is installed, and no training data has to be passed over to Google, Microsoft, Amazon, or Facebook to train the chatbot.

2.4 Design Principles

Two approaches can be used to develop a chatbot depending on the algorithms and techniques adopted: the rule-based approach and the machine-learning approach.

2.4.1 Rule-Based System

A rule-based chatbot processes information and responds based on a set of predefined rules with the use of pattern-matching algorithms. Although the pattern-matching techniques vary in complexity, the basic idea is the same. The user input is classified as a pattern, and the chatbot selects a predefined answer by matching the pattern with a set of stored responses. The pattern and response matching algorithms are handcrafted. Pattern matching is adopted by many chatbots and is especially popular among early chatbots like ELIZA, PARRY, and ALICE. The advantage of the rule-based approach is its speed as it does not require any deep analysis of the input text. However, the responses are repeated and lack flexibility and originality as the knowledge is set by the developer in advance. The following paragraphs

will provide an overview of the three most commonly used languages for the implementation of rule-based chatbots. MacDonald (2019)

Artificial Intelligence Mark-up Language (AIML) is a derivation of Extensible Mark-up Language (XML). ALICE was the first chatbot implemented in the AIML language. AIML has a class of data objects called AIML objects, and these objects are responsible for modelling conversational patterns. Each object consists of two units called topics and categories. A topic is an optional top-level element that has a name attribute and a set of categories associated with it. Categories are the most basic unit of knowledge and are the rules of the chatbot. Each category consists of two elements called pattern and template. The pattern matches the input from the user to the template that contains the response of the chatbot. AIML is simple, flexible, and highly maintainable, and thus is one of the most commonly adopted languages for chatbot development.

The biggest disadvantages of AIML are that the developer must specify a pattern for every possible input of the user and that it is inefficient when the knowledge base is large. The structure of an AIML object is demonstrated below: User Input Corresponding Response to Input. RiveScript is a line-based scripting language that can be used to implement the Knowledge Base. Compared to AIML, RiveScript has more built-in features and tags, which means that the writer does not need to specify information about the chatbot in the additional configuration files. ChatScript is an open-source language for developing rule-based chatbots. It matches user inputs to outputs using rules created by human writers in program scripts through a process called Dialogflow scripting. ChatScript uses concepts that are set of words that have the same meaning. It consists of 2000 predefined concepts and scripters can also write their concepts easily. Compared to AIML and RiveScript, ChatScript is a harder language, but it allows developers to combine rules in more complicated ways.

2.4.2 Machine Learning System

Machine Learning The recent advancement in machine learning has made it possible to develop more intelligent chatbots. Chatbots that adopt machine learning approaches use machine learning algorithms to extract information and generate responses and can improve through previous conversations. An extensive training set is required for machine-learning-based chatbots. Two types of models can be used, retrieval or generative. Retrieval-based models involve choosing the optimal response from a set of responses, and generative models, on the other hand, use deep learning techniques to generate the response. Li (2020)

2.5 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI), sometimes called machine intelligence, is intelligence demonstrated by machines, in contrast to the natural intelligence displayed by humans. Leading Artificial Intelligence textbooks define the field as the study of "intelligent agents": any device that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chance of successfully achieving its goals. (Legg & Hutter, 2007) Colloquially, the term "artificial intelligence" is often used to describe machines (or computers) that mimic "cognitive" functions that humans associate with the human mind, such as "learning" and "problem-solving". (Norvig, 2009)

2.5.1 Artificial Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks are one of the main tools used in machine learning. As the "neural" part of their name suggests, they are brain-inspired systems which are intended to replicate the way that humans learn. Neural networks consist of input and output layers, as well as (in most cases) a hidden layer consisting of units that transform the input into something that the output layer can use. They are excellent tools for finding patterns which are far too complex or numerous for a human programmer to extract and teach the machine to recognize. (Digitaltrends, 2019). An ANN is based on a collection of connected units or nodes called

artificial neurons, which loosely model the neurons in a biological brain. Each connection, like the synapses in a biological brain, can transmit a signal to other neurons.

An artificial neural network is an attempt to simulate the network of neurons that make up a human brain so that the computer will be able to learn things and make decisions in a human-like manner. ANNs are created by programming regular computers to behave as though they are interconnected brain cells. (Forbes, 2019) An artificial neuron that receives a signal process it and can signal neurons connected to it. With this, ANN can be learned based on provided data, they can learn to distinguish objects based on provided data. Their efficiency will depend on the quality and range of data provided for testing and training.

2.5.2 Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML) is the scientific study of algorithms and statistical models that computer systems use to perform a specific task without using explicit instructions, relying on patterns and inference instead. It is seen as a subset of artificial intelligence. Machine learning algorithms build a mathematical model based on sample data, known as "training data", to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed to perform the task (Bishop, 2006).

Numerous Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing frameworks today use machine learning. Machine learning frameworks figure out how to perform errands by dissecting models. For instance, In Artificial Intelligence Computer Vision, a framework would figure out how to perceive a face by examining numerous pictures of the face; it would not be modified with express standards, for example, "wears glasses" and "has silver hair". There are many algorithms and techniques which can be used in machine learning, including deep learning, decision trees, support vector machines and neural networks.

2.5.3 Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Processing is concerned with the interaction between computers and human languages. The ultimate objective of Natural Language Processing NLP is to read and decipher language patterns that enable us to make sense of human languages in a valuable manner. (Understanding Natural Language Understanding, 2014)

2.5.4 Cognitive Computing

Cognitive computing can be defined as systems that use computerized models to simulate the human cognition process to find solutions in complex situations where the answers may be ambiguous and uncertain. Cognitive computing allows systems to synthesize data from various information sources while weighing context and conflicting evidence to suggest the best possible answers. This is all achievable due to self-learning technologies (Machine Learning) that use data mining, pattern recognition and natural language processing (NLP) to enhance machine intelligence.

2.5.5 Firebase Database

Firebase is a mobile and web application development platform developed by Firebase, Inc. in 2011, then acquired by Google in 2014. (Tamplin, 2014) As of October 2018, the Firebase platform has 18 products, (Firebase Products, 2018) which are used by 1.5 million apps. (Francis, 2018). Firebase provides a real-time database and backend as a service. The service provides application developers with an API that allows application data to be synchronized across clients and stored on Firebase's cloud. (Firebase Real-time Database, 2014) The company provides client libraries that enable integration with Android, iOS, JavaScript, Java, Objective-C, Swift and Node.js applications.

The database is also accessible through a REST API and bindings for several JavaScript frameworks such as AngularJS, React, Ember.js and Backbone.js. (Matt, 2014) The REST API uses the Server-Sent Events protocol, which is an API for creating HTTP connections for

receiving push notifications from a server. Developers using the real-time database can secure their data by using the company's server-side-enforced security rules. (Barb, 2012)

2.5.6 Google Dialogflow

Dialogflow (formerly Api.ai, Speaktait) is a Google-owned developer of human–compute interaction technologies based on natural language conversations. The company is best known for creating the Assistant (by Speaktait), a virtual buddy for Android, iOS, and Windows Phone smartphones that performs tasks and answers users' questions in a natural language. Dialogflow can be used to create Chatbots for web and mobile applications as shown in the system architecture above (Google Developers, 2023). The user asks a query through either a web/mobile interface, using either text or voice-based communication. Queries in the dialogue flow are analysed using Natural Language Processing to give the best answer to the particular query. The response is sent back to the user. Dialog flow also operates on external APIs (Application programmable interfaces). dialogue flow can be implemented in most of today's virtual messaging platforms and virtual assistances. It is best suited for this project in the manner that there is a large community online in cases of questions or issues.

2.5.7 Android Mobile Operating System

Mobile phones have been adopted by the masses as they pause as the main medium of communication. Mobile phones have been developed into gadgets that meet day-to-day needs. Mobile phones mimic mini-computers that can be carried around. People can get access to information with a few taps. An average mobile has internet connectivity, which allows people to have unlimited access to a connected world. Mobile phones run one operating system to operate external applications and services. Android is a mobile operating system developed by Google. It is based on a modified version of the Linux kernel and other

open-source software and is designed primarily for touchscreen mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets.

2.6 Chatbot Engineering and Design Approaches

(Raschka, 2020) To develop a chatbot, the developer must be aware of several techniques. Some techniques used to build chatbots have been listed above. The parsing involves input text analysis and uses several NLP functions to manipulate the inputs, such as Python NLTK decision trees. Besides, it includes Dependency Tree, Syntactical Parsing, Parts-of-Speech Tagging, Named Entity Recognition, Entity Parsing, and Topic Modelling. Pattern matching is the technique employed by almost all chatbots. Khan (2018) In a question-answering chatbot, systems depend on the types of correspondence, such as natural language inputs, simple statements, or domain-specific inquiries. AIML Artificial intelligence Mark-up Language, insights from Pattern Matching and Pattern Recognition technique. The stimulus-response approach is to model natural language to understand the human and Bot dialogue system (Khan, 2018).

Chat script comes into play when no matches happen with the user input phrase in AIML. It emphasizes the structure best sentence for constructing a sensitive default response. It involves a network of functionalities, for instance, factor ideas, logic, etc.

SQL can be used to memorize earlier conversations with the chatbot. Markov Chain is also used to construct better probabilistic and precise responses. Markov Chain states a fixed probability of every letter or word occurrence in the same textual dataset. Language tricks are a form of phrases and fragments of sentences available for the chatbot to attach a knowledge base that makes that part more convincing. Canned responses that predetermine answers to some particular questions are known, Typo errors and simulating keystrokes, personal history, and non-Sequitur are not logical conclusions used as language tricks. These linguistic tricks are used to assure user input and provide alternative responses to respective questions.

An ontology represents a structural representation of the domain's entities and the relationships between them. It is a treelike arrangement that assembles all entities into one realm, their subclasses, and instances.

Additionally, it establishes connections between the tree leaves by specifying one-way, two ways, and transient relationships. Moreover, it creates links between the tree leaves by defining unilateral and bilateral pathways and temporary relations.

2.7 Common Technologies Used in Chatbots

Since Dialogflow Essential, IBM Watson, Amazon Lex, ManyChat, etc., provide ML algorithms training, this section addresses how user intentions, entities, & fulfilment are utilized to build and train a chatbot. Intents are potential user statements that can trigger the user's purpose. When an end-user connects with the chatbot, they intend to; use the chatbot to know the information they want (Raschka, 2020). Suppose an end-user asks the chatbot to "Book a movie ticket," in this scenario if this conversation happens at a theatre, it can be understood that the customer wants to book a movie ticket. Now, to understand the same for the chatbot, the designer uses intent to identify what the user is requesting. As a result, "Book a movie ticket" could be named "book_movie" intent. Intents are the aim, purpose, goal, and motives of the users interacting with the chatbot system. Now every user's intention is categorized into two parts:

- i. Seeking information – for instance, patron purpose of finding the information about train tickets, of seeking weather condition of Toronto for next week etc.
- ii. Taking action – such as booking a table at a food restaurant and booking movie tickets. Entities are modifiers to intents, which are used to add knowledge or information to intent. The chatbot finds the exact matches for the training phrase of the user input.

Suppose two phrases of user input, “Book a movie ticket,” or “Book a flight ticket,” in this intent is “book” Similarly here “movie” or “flight” act as a modifier, hence acts as entities. Designing chatbot entities is equally crucial to feed upon the database concerning intent. if this doesn’t happen, the chatbot fails miserably if it cannot give the required information after identifying the user’s intention. Raschka (2020) In simple words, Utterance is the synonym for “phrase” or “sentence”; which means the exact terms or questions asked by different users in different forms. Examples of utterances from different travel agents are; “Book a flight from London to Paris today,” “Could you please, book a flight from London to Paris today,” and “I want to fly on April 27, 2023, from Mumbai to Hong Kong.” After feeding intents, and entities, the utterance designer must train the chatbot model such that it will recognize the existing set of defined intents/entities when new statements are provided. The confidence score tells us how confident or the amount in percentage the model is recognizing user intents with the intents existing in the trained database.

2.8 Data Management and Training Methods for Dialogue Systems

There are several ways to approach dataset expansion. Data augmentation is one of these ways as it preserves the information the data carries while changing the way it appears. There has been a lot of research done in the area of data augmentation techniques applied to image datasets, but in this work, the main interest lies in the application to dialogue corpora. Another approach to dataset expansion is data collection which can be done manually or automatically.

Data Augmentation-Based Methods

Word shuffling: When it comes to word shuffling, this way of creating new sentences for the dataset will not require any additional sources, but only the initial data. There are several ways to formulate a grammatically correct sentence in the English language, and it is possible to move around words while maintaining the grammatical correctness and the meaning of the

sentence. When using this method, each sentence is tokenized into separate words and then these words are shuffled and gathered back to create a new sentence. With a modification, a third-party tool can be used to validate the sentences that retain grammatical correctness after the transformation. The validated sentences will then will be used to extend the initial dataset. When applied to input parts of the dataset, the grammatical correctness can often be unimportant as users can provide inputs that are imperfect in following the language rules. When such cases are possible, it can be beneficial to train the classifier using this method of data augmentation.

Word replacement: Using this technique requires a source of synonyms for all or some of the words from the initial dataset. It will also require some data preprocessing to identify the bases of all words and their synonyms. Replacing all words with a random synonym can alter the meaning of the original sentence resulting in worse results with the classified. The most relevant way to approach this problem is to identify several keywords that can be replaced. When the reprocessing is done, the algorithm will generate new sentences for the dataset replacing the keywords with their synonyms. With some additional work during tokenizing, it is possible to apply this technique to expressions or even whole sentences providing more quality data for the output dataset. One more way of following this approach is using semantic networks that link different words with an “is-a” relation. In this case, the words can be replaced with their “parents” following up along the network instead of working with synonyms. Additionally, recent research in this area proposes to use predictive models to predict the next word of the sentence having the beginning of the sentence as input.

The output prediction can then replace the following word in the sentence thus forming a different sentence to add to the initial dataset. This method can still create unreasonable sentences which have to be filtered by a human supervisor before they can be used. In this

case, the word table was replaced with a chart which doesn't make any sense here as it is a different kind of table.

Syntax tree manipulation: This method manipulates the sentence core structure changing the time, the clause or the voice of the sentence. This method requires a round of Natural Language Processing (NLP) which is a computationally expensive task. It can be applied to several sentences generating a number of their altered versions while preserving the meaning and grammatical correctness. To apply the method, start with generating a syntactic dependency tree for each sentence in the input data. Then make some transformations to the sentence structure such as moving from active to passive voice, splitting a sentence containing a clause, and changing the tense of the sentence. When all transformations are complete, build a new sentence from the mutated syntax tree and add it to the dataset.

This method would face problems if the input sentence has grammatical problems. In this case, the tree build could fail or might not reflect what the user meant by the sentence. Thus, the input might need a round of reprocessing before its syntax tree can be manipulated to generate new entries for the dataset.

Data Collection-Based Methods

Active learning: Active learning is based on continual human-bot interaction. The idea of active learning comes from schools where students are encouraged to actively participate in the learning process besides passively listening to the teachers. This idea has then been applied in the area of machine learning to optimize the interaction between machine learning systems and humans. An active learning system requires the help of a human supervisor to label its data. Application to chatbots, namely intent-based chatbots receive direct benefits from this approach as each input sentence is mapped to one or more intents (or labels). Other dialogue systems can also benefit from active learning by receiving user feedback about their response to the user. A common approach to active learning in dialogue systems consists of

the following steps. The user starts by sending a message to the bot. The bot will then generate several responses using its preliminary trained classifier. The bot then sends the responses to the user in order of decreasing confidence probability. The user picks one of the responses as 'best' or suggests a better response, sending it back to the bot.

The pair of input-response is then propagated through the layers of the bot's network increasing the probability of a correct response for that particular input. The user sends another message to the bot and the process repeats. In active learning, the selection criteria of the user are subjective which is one of the challenges active learning is facing in practice. Other challenges include multi-tasking, unknown classes and variable labelling cost.

Crowdsourcing: Crowdsourcing can be viewed as a simple straightforward collection of data. Crowdsourcing in machine learning, apart from collecting data, can be used for different learning tasks, such as data labelling, image classification, chatbot training and others. This method can often be less expensive than other data collection methods, it can also be done both online and offline. For offline data collection, several workers are supplied with instructions for what kind of data machine learning requires. Although it could seem that the process finishes when the workers are done, it is often not true. The crowdsourced data has to be checked to meet some quality standards. There are a few things that can go wrong about data quality.

Apart from the possibility of incompetent workers, incomplete or ambiguous guidelines could result in different interpretations of concepts and inconsistent data labelling. This problem has been addressed and has to be considered when using crowdsourcing for data collection. Online data collection can potentially use bigger crowds for machine learning tasks. A creative way of online crowdsourcing was introduced by Google's implementation of reCAPTCHA. Using reCAPTCHA Google protects its services against automatic web crawlers at the same time collecting free crowdsourced data for its machine learning tasks for

image identification. An honourable mention of the application of crowdsourcing is a chatbot from 2016 developed by Microsoft called Tay. Tay was supposed to learn more about language over time by engaging people in dialogue using tweets and private messages.

It was designed to emulate observed patterns in subsequent conversations with other users. The faulty part was insufficient input sanitization which a few hours after release made Tay sound just like the internet. Over time most of the tweeted messages became offensive, racist or sexist as Tay was learning from random people on the internet. Having done as much damage, Tay was suspended 16 hours after the release, but it taught the ML community a valuable lesson.

When crowdsourcing is applied to dialogue systems, it can prove as an effective way of training a chatbot. A large pool of crowdsourced workers continually interacts with the bot to teach it a more natural language and feed it more data for training. Alternatively, the workers can create datasets to feed to the bot as learning or training data.

Online learning: Online learning has been studied in several fields such as game theory and machine learning. The goal of online learning is to make a sequence of predictions about the answer to a defined question. For every given answer, the correct answer is revealed and the classifier suffers a loss measured on the difference between the two answers. The difference with the active learning method here is that the correct answer is known and there is no supervisor giving feedback. As opposed to regular training methods where the data is provided in batches, in online learning data is served in a sequential order. The classifier is being trained and retrained step by step getting closer to giving the correct answer at each step.

For this method to work, there must be a correlation between the questions asked, otherwise, the learning might worsen the performance of the classifier instead of improving it. Online learning is useful when the dataset gradually changes over time or the new data is being

streamed over time and has to be taken into consideration as soon as possible. No work has been found in the area of online learning applied to chatbots or other dialogue systems. Thus, this work will explore how well it can be applied to chatbots and find out about the advantages and disadvantages that it entails.

2.8.1 Training Dialogue Systems

Several different methods can be used to train dialogue systems, among widely used ones are rule-based, sequence-to-sequence-based, reinforcement learning based and hierarchical reinforcement learning-based methods. Gauba (2018)

Rule-based methods: A good example of a system developed using rule-based methods is ELIZA. ELIZA analyses user replies and attempts to match them with defined patterns. User input is analysed using decomposition rules which depend on certain keywords being present in the input. The response is generated using some of the user input along with reassembly rules corresponding to used decomposition rules. ELIZA is an early development and therefore has several issues including dependence on keywords, the inability of using the context of the conversation, and the difficulty of choosing non-controversial rules. On the other hand, it has laid the foundations for all rule-based dialogue systems. The advantage of using rule-based methods is having control over the selection of responses, it keeps the developed system consistent and ensures that the user is not being offended by its responses. A more recent development in systems rule-based method is NADIA. NADIA enables an expert to create a set of question-answer pairs that contribute to achieving the defined goals. The conversation is considered finished once all the goals were achieved. There is a possibility to add optional questions that do not contribute to the completion of goals, but rather provide additional information to the user. The expert-defined model will then be used to engage in a conversation with the user by the NADIA system which will follow a set of

hard-coded rules to make a natural conversation with the user and attempt to achieve all the goals.

To summarise rule-based methods, when the desired dialogue flow has a known number of states and user replies, the rule-based methods outperform other training methods. However, in scenarios when it is infeasible to enumerate all possible states and replies, it is not effective to use rule-based methods. When the user input fails to match the rules, the system has no other choice than to give an *“I don’t know, please ask something else”*-kind of response. In this work, the developed customer support chatbot will deal with simple dialogue tasks such as asking about the services the business offers, how to reach a human agent and providing details concerning the business. These tasks contribute to the goal of accessing information and can be completed only one at a time. This makes the rule-based approach a reasonable choice considering the described advantages and disadvantages.

Sequence-to-sequence-based methods: Sequence-to-sequence learning has caught the attention of researchers since the publication of the RNN Encoder-Decoder used for statistical machine translation. Sequence-to-sequence method described in the article has since been successfully applied to other tasks. Sequence-to-sequence methods, often referred to as seq2seq, are deep learning methods which learn to transform a given input into an output using an encoder and a decoder. The transformation is done according to the defined dictionaries which contain words, expressions and sentences mapped to other figures of speech. Apart from the dictionaries, seq2seq also makes use of dialogue history which consists of every word chosen before the current state of the dialogue (Li, 2020).

A probability distribution over dictionaries affected by the history is the key to choosing the response sequence in seq2seq methods. A notable application of seq2seq methods is translation tasks from English to French where the seq2seq method achieved great results compared to other methods. It has later been adopted in building dialogue systems such as

chatbots. For building chatbots, the problem was defined as the translation of certain user inputs to a defined output. This was achieved by adding a hidden state between the encoder and the decoder which stores “the meaning” of the user input. During the learning process, the model is taught to map this hidden state to an output sequence, in its nature this approach is similar to intent-based chatbots. The difference is that a certain intent is mapped to a defined number of outputs, in the case of seq2seq, this mapping is not static and varies depending on the conversation history.

The recent advances in conversational NLP show that seq2seq models trained on a large-sized dataset can create great quality assistants capable of answering simple questions and extracting relevant information. Li (2020)

But although seq2seq methods give good results in domain-specific tasks, such as flight booking, models built on them can be difficult to customize when the learning process does not cover all possible dialogue flows, which can lead to incorrect and often confusing responses. The case study chatbot that was developed in this work has to complete simple tasks in providing information to users and cannot afford to have confusing or unclear responses, thus this approach is not optimal in this case.

Reinforcement learning methods: Reinforcement learning is an old technique initially developed to train robots to move. This machine learning method increases its efficiency over time by using a system of rewards which can be positive or negative (Raschka, 2020). The model is trained to maximize the reward by learning the best actions to take at each turn of the conversation. Each performed action is evaluated by a supervisor or an algorithm and yields negative or positive reward points based on the expectations. Chatbots that use this method become increasingly efficient the longer the conversation goes as long as there is a way to evaluate their response. Reinforcement learning methods have gained more attention when combined with new deep learning methods in beating humans in Atari games. It is even

possible to further improve the deep learning methods by matching them against each other. But as reinforcement learning is suitable for game tasks, it is notable that in games the diversity of possible actions is limited and defined. de Bayser (2017)

In the case of dialogues, the number of possible responses is large and depending on the limitations, matches the number of possible sentences in a language. Using this method, with the ever-increasing number of possible sentences (actions) the algorithm discovers, the more complex become the tasks of response generation. Using reinforcement learning allows people to make more natural chatbots as they continually learn and improve from user feedback (Raschka, 2020). The chatbots are capable of handling long conversations while building their responses on previously acquired information. With the addition of deep reinforced learning, the model can optimize the future reward while at the same time maintaining such properties of a good conversation as informativity, coherence and ease of answering. However, the reinforcement learning method presents several limitations. Firstly, it takes time before the system is trained well enough to uphold a meaningful conversation with a human. Secondly, even simple conversations with a single goal may require a large amount of quality training data due to the complexity of human dialogues. Lastly, grammatical correctness is in question as pure reinforcement learning methods do not include space for additional grammatical rules on the output. In the case of the case study chatbot that was developed in this work, the responses can be static and can be defined by a set of rules. This approach could work well but it is outperformed by a rule-based approach as the set of rules is not hard to define.

Hierarchical reinforcement learning-based methods: Hierarchical reinforcement learning approach is based on previously described reinforcement learning with the addition of the temporal abstraction concept. It attempts at solving the problem of dimensionality in reinforcement learning where each dimension represents one action that can be taken in a

given state. Using hierarchical reinforcement learning, to decide a given state the model will follow the defined domain hierarchy and enter sub-domains with their policies until the decision can be made. Policies at lower domain levels are optimized for simpler tasks which together contribute to deciding the master domain level. Hinton (2006)

The policies at the master domain will choose between using primitive or composed actions to maximize the reward. In case when a composed action is chosen, the reward is delayed until all the sub-actions are complete and the information is passed back to the master domain. Where reinforcement learning models learn only primitive actions and need to decide the output for each step of the conversation, the hierarchical reinforcement learning model can learn both primitive and composite actions which decreases the number of dimensions at each level of the model and adds more control to the decision process.

Hierarchical reinforcement learning-based methods outperform standard reinforcement learning methods in training speed and output precision (Hinton, 2006). It uses several layers of abstraction to handle the increasing number of parameters which enables its use in large dialogue systems where standard reinforcement learning would be infeasible to apply. Although hierarchical reinforcement learning solves some problems, it opens several new questions concerning handling deeper hierarchies, designing reward strategies for lower-level hierarchies and developing an automatic way of dividing complex actions into a hierarchy of composed actions. For the same reason as in the case of the reinforcement learning method, this work sticks with the rule-based approach for the development of the chatbot.

2.9 Contextuality in Intent-Based Chatbots

The evolution of NLP and NLU helped drive chatbot technologies to a new stage where they can sometimes successfully replace humans in simple tasks such as hotel booking or customer support. Chatbots can be categorized in several different ways. They can be developed to handle chit-chat or be task-oriented (Liang, 2018). They can deal with open or

closed domains. They can be intent-based or flow based. While a simple chatbot implementation can be achieved through simple pattern matching with defined responses, such chatbots are very limited and cannot handle any degree of natural conversation with humans. On the other hand, more sophisticated chatbots using machine learning achieve great results in natural conversations with humans while limited to a specific domain and conversation flow. One type of chatbot well suited for goal-oriented tasks is an intent-based chatbot. Such bots operate with utterances, intent and entities. When having a conversation with a user, an input from the user is considered an utterance and will be processed by the bot to output a response. An utterance is mapped to one or more intents where intent explains the motive of the user with the given input. Intent is about what the user wants at a specific step of the conversation and it is often defined as a verb or a noun, such as “latest_news” or “set_alarm”. Utterances may contain entities which provide additional information within the intent. An example of such information could be “Monday” with the intent “weather_on_day” or “10 AM” with the intent “set_alarm”. The output of an intent-based chatbot is usually a static list of one or more elements from which one is chosen at random, but it can differ depending on the entities within the utterance. While having a semi-static output, with the help of machine learning the chatbot can comprehend a large diversity of inputs successfully mapping them to the intents and providing relevant responses for the user. Although an intent-based chatbot can digest all kinds of inputs, it is prone to context-specific ones. The bottleneck is when the same input in different contexts would require completely different responses. In case when the chatbot is taught to recognize the response, it cannot consider context out of the box. This problem can be fixed by adding contextuality to the chatbot in the form of a state machine. This technique comes from another type of chatbot — flow-based ones. A flow-based chatbot uses a predefined conversation flow, which can be visualized as a flowchart. For instance, when a user starts the conversation with the bot,

he/she will be guided through the states step by step until a certain defined end-goal state is reached. This restrictiveness has its pros, such as clear abilities, maintaining the context, and predictability, as well as its cons, such as limited options, unnatural conversation, and difficulties with handling complex requests. Combining the flow-based approach with the intent-based approach is expected to challenge some of the cons while at the same time maintaining the pros of both approaches.

User inputs can be divided into contextual and non-contextual. Contextual inputs, such as short answers to questions asked by the bot, can be handled by the flow-based part of the chatbot. This will allow the classifier to limit possible hits to the ones residing within the context. Non-contextual inputs, such as asking about the available menu, can be handled by the intent-based part of the chatbot. In this case, the classifier will exclude the contextual inputs and only take into consideration the rest of the defined intents. In this structure, each transition in the state machine corresponds to one or more defined intents, while the intents may have two properties: context-dependent and context-changing ones. Intents without those properties reside outside of the state machine and can be accessed regardless of the current state.

Context is a generic term, which can be operationalized in several ways when it comes to chatbots. One type is situational context, which is the context of user location. It is about knowing the physical location of the user or in which part of the website or application he currently is. Chatbots can use this information to provide correct responses, such as when the user asks about restaurants nearby. Another type is lingual context — the context of the conversation flow. Different words in a sentence can have different meanings depending on what was mentioned in the sentence or some sentences ago. A lot of information can come from a particular experience of a user or things that surround her/him. This presents a challenge to chatbots, as they are only able to respond based on information they can access.

One more type is persistence context. This context is about the current state of the conversation. Persistence context helps bind inputs and outputs into a conversation flow, where some of them depend on others. As an example, a simple input “Yes” does not carry any meaning or intent without the previously asked question. The last type is emotional context. Different words or their order can be used to empathise emotions of the user within an input. Intentionally programmed chatbots would be able to recognise the context and respond appropriately, while other chatbots might misinterpret the user’s intent.

2.10 A Concept of Continual Learning

Lange (2019) One of the contributions of this work is the application of the concept of continual learning to chatbots. It adopts the idea of online learning with the difference that the data provided for this learning is being crowdsourced. The Literature review subsection covers the mentioned concepts of online learning and crowdsourcing. The idea is to keep training the chatbot as the conversation goes on while having the same dictionary, state machine and list of intents. Retraining the bot continually will enable it to learn more different ways of expressing defined intents and adapt to different structures of sentences. Doing it in real-time allows the bot to change its responses should the user try to clarify his request (Lange, 2019). The retraining affects the probabilities within the classifier which results in some requests hitting the threshold of identification which otherwise would result in a standard “*Please ask something else*”-kind of message. Figure 2.1 demonstrates the steps of an interaction between a user and a continual learning chatbot.

Having described the idea, it can now be clarified by providing a step-by-step approach to continual learning. Assuming there’s a trained intent-based contextual classifier, proceed in the following steps. The process is initiated by the user sending some input to the bot. The bot will then process the input and consider the probabilistic distribution of matched intents, picking the most likely one and preparing the response to the user. Then the bot sends his

response to the user and then continues to analyse the request. If the identified intent probability exceeds the defined threshold number, the bot matches the input with the intent and re-calibrates its classifier to learn this new combination (Lange, 2019).

If the intent probability does not exceed the threshold, this combination is discarded as potentially not precise or harmful. Choosing a high probability for the threshold allows more precise learning while lowering it allows for more learning samples, but at the same time can learn the classifier wrong. This number has to be carefully picked and tested before using it in real-case applications (Zhang, 2010). The disadvantage of retraining in real-time is unpredictability. It is hard to tell how the classifier will react to different inputs after retraining as users receive some control over training the bot. It is possible that after several retraining the bot can “forget” some of the intents it was previously trained. In the field of artificial intelligence, this effect is called “catastrophic forgetting” or “catastrophic interference” and it is discussed in more detail in the following subsection.

Brown (2021) An alternative way of using this approach is to collect and process the data in some way before using it to calibrate the classifier. This way, no unwanted data will be used for training and the results of the training process will become more controlled and predictable. Described the continual learning concept, the following section describes its implementation with a case study chatbot. During the testing of the implementation in different scenarios a small handcrafted dataset was used and its results were recorded, which are presented in the *Results* section. To validate this approach, the results were compared to the baseline scenario without continual learning in the *Analysis* section.

Figure 2.1: Steps of an interaction between a user and a continual learning chatbot

2.11 Concerns about Catastrophic Forgetting

Jerusalem (2018) The concept of continual learning adds a new challenge to neural networks called “catastrophic forgetting”. This challenge appears due to the tendency for existing trained skills to be lost as new data is added to the classifier. In intent-based systems, this happens specifically when the network was trained on one of the intents, but at the same time lacked training for the rest of intents. This causes the weights in the network to change to adjust all possible scenarios for trained intent which in turn results in the reduction of probabilities for all other intents. This reduction will sometimes decrease the probability below the allowed threshold making the network fail to recognize “close” inputs. Consider the example of a case when the probability of a certain input-intent combination is 0.81 and the set threshold is 0.8. After applying continual learning on other intents, new information will be considered when calculating the probability for the previously mentioned case thus decreasing the probability below 0.8 and rendering the input unrecognized. Lange (2019)

This problem has been investigated and there are several approaches to tackle it. Earlier attempts suggest storing previous data and retraining the system every time new data comes in. However, such methods require a large amount of memory for storing old data and more computational iterations which prove inefficient in large systems due to a substantial increase in retraining time. Several new approaches include “learning without forgetting”, “progressive neural networks”, “elastic weight consolidation” etc. Lange (2019) Considering the research done on this topic, this work does not implement any of the methods to overcome catastrophic forgetting and instead concentrates on the concept of continual learning in chatbots (Jerusalem, 2018). This concludes the section literature overview and completes O1 specified among the thesis objectives in the Introduction section.

2.12 Chatbot Application on Websites

Industry 4.0 is a name for the current trend of automation and data exchange in manufacturing technologies. It includes cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things, cloud computing and cognitive computing and Mineral Processing. Industry 4.0 creates what has been called a “smart factory”. The future of work will likely be a hybrid that involves both human and machine intelligence working in conjunction toward the same shared goals.

In late years, chatbot human interaction research is at its high, due to the advance in Artificial Intelligence and consequently the improvement in chatbot interaction capacity. Therefore, since achieving some complexity in conversational design is no longer hidden by the technology available, many studies focus solely on the user experience aspect of human-chatbot interaction. aspects of conversational design (The Role of Chatbots in Industry 4.0, 2017).

Chatbots are conversational agents that can be assistants of customer support specialists in the industry from different fronts. When a chatbot has been integrated into a website, communication and access to information become a lot easier. This naturally interests customers and boosts customer user experience. Customers can get a better user experience with the support of a chatbot assistant. (The Role of Chatbots in Industry 4.0, 2017)

Why Chatbots?

- i. Easy to use
- ii. Real-time interaction with information to queries
- iii. Easily accessible
- iv. Natural communication with “things”
- v. Continuous improvement
- vi. Personnel relations with engineers or respective users

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overview

The web-based chatbot system was developed to run on the web. The system design and development comprise of a JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) file that stores user intents as well as the bot's responses to those intents. The system was written in Python and was powered by Python's backend framework, Flask. Flask is a lightweight Python web framework that provides useful tools and features for creating web applications in the Python language.

The system consists of a chat module that allows users to easily interact with the system. Information will be periodically fed into the JSON file for a set of questions that people will ask at any point. The User Interface or the actual system was developed using Visual Studio code using HTML (HyperText Markup Language), CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) and JavaScript programming language. The Artificial Intelligence model was trained using PyTorch, a Python machine learning library to generate the best model of high accuracy for the web-based chatbot system. The model was converted into NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) model data type that created the bag of words inserted into the web project for inference. The model was programmed using Python on Visual Studio code.

3.2 System Architecture

The system architecture shows the simplest flow roles of the user and the admin. The user simply chats with the bot whilst the admin has several roles such as editing, updating, deleting and adding information. The system shows extended user roles and the system architecture of the user and the admin.

The data flow diagram for the project is shown in Figure 3.1 below and Figure 3.2 displays the user roles model.

Figure 3.1: Data flow diagram

Figure 3.2: User Roles model

3.3 PyTorch Modelling

Firstly, Python and Visual Studio code was installed. Followed by the installation of Flask and PyTorch, a Python machine-learning library. Then, NLTK was installed. However, the model was trained and modelled using PyTorch and later on converted to an NLTK model file (.py) that creates the bag of words that was inserted into the web project.

Visual Studio code was used for programming the model using Python. The model was trained and tested using a dataset of collected intents and their answers. Intents ranged from basic greetings to questions about the website. The model was then converted to a Flask app and then imported into the web project. The model was used for inference, to ensure that the bot responds with greater accuracy.

3.4 Python Programming

The web application was developed using Python through Visual Studio code. The chat system was integrated using Python's Flask. The activities consist of Python code that enables users to interact with the chatbot and also generate responses through the JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) file. There is an area for text input and a send button that allows users to proceed with sending their intents. The chat interface is also displayed in the figures below. The PyTorch model is inserted in the Flask app that runs the web application as an NLTK model.

3.5 Web Development

The land-on-page for the application was developed using HTML5 and CSS3 and JavaScript. It was simply designed to be a descriptive site for the web software. The page was developed using Visual Studio code. The application was designed to be hosted on the web and accessible to most devices.

CHAPTER FOUR

IMPLEMENTATION, RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Implementation

This section describes the implementation of the custom case study chatbot and its modules, which is necessary to address the thesis objective O2.

4.2 Software prerequisites for running the case study chatbot

Here, is a summary of the choice of tools. To implement the chatbot, the Python programming language was used. As for the OS, the program was run by Microsoft Windows with the latest available version (Windows 11 Pro). In Python, this work used PyTorch for machine learning tasks and NLTK for word tokenization and stemming. It also used NumPy for dealing with arrays supplied as input for TFLearn. To install all the Python packages in the OS of choice, the latest version of PIP was used. The software and library versions used for the case study chatbot implementation are specified in Table 4.1.

4.3 Initial preparations before the implementation

There is a number of different chatbots that can be created using the latest machine-learning technologies. Some can act as virtual assistants; others provide customer support for businesses. For the case study project, a chatbot that will allow the user to make inquiries was created. The development process begins with installing the required packages. PIP was used to install Flask, NumPy, NLTK, TensorFlow and PyTorch in the OS command line.

```
pip install flask
```

```
pip install numpy
```

```
pip install nltk
```

```
pip install pytorch
```

When the required packages are installed, the initial training data is then defined. With TFLearn and PyTorch, a percentage of the dataset to be used for training and validation can

be specified, thus defining and creating the starting dataset. The preview of the dataset enumerating all the intents is provided in Figure 4.1. This preview shows a JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) file that maps a list of defined user inputs to a list of outputs. Each tag represents the intent of the user message. This training data will be used to train the neural network to (1) identify the user input as one of the listed intents and (2) return an output from the corresponding list of responses.

Apart from the intents, the initial list of all words was listed that this model will support, is demonstrated in Figure 4.2. A list of conversation prompts generated for this project was used to get started, and later all the words from the patterns in the intents file were appended to complete this list. This list of conversation prompts is reduced in size after stemming, as a number of them have the same root. From this experiment, the list will contain close to 136 unique stemmed words, 123 patterns, and 32 tags during run time. The code below allows the importation of the rest of the data needed for the implementation.

4.4 Intent-based chatbot implementation

With all the preparations done and data loaded, start the implementation of the first version of the chatbot, which maps the user input to intent from the intent list and prints the corresponding output sequence. To separate the loaded data, an initial array of words from the list of conversation prompts is created and three blank arrays for tags, patterns, and corresponding intents.

To incorporate different responses in the initial pattern list, each sentence in the intents patterns is looped through and inserted in each response in place of placeholders. This is demonstrated in Figure 4.4.

Name	Version
VS Code	1.76.2
Microsoft Windows (OS)	Windows 11 Pro
Python	3.11.4
Package Installer for Python (PIP)	20.0.2
Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK)	3.8.1
Flask	2.2.3
PyTorch	2.0.0
Keras	2.11.0
NumPy	1.18.1
Pandas	1.0.1
SciPy	1.4.1
TensorFlow	2.0.0
TFLearn	0.3.2

Table 4.1: Version of used software and libraries

```
File Edit Selection View Go Run Terminal Help intents.json - Project
base.html 2 app.py JS app.js # style.css # chatstyle.css home.htm
intents.json > [ ] intents
1 {
2   "intents": [
3     {
4       "tag": "greeting",
5       "patterns": ["Hi", "Hey", "Is anyone there?", "Hello", "Good day"],
6       "responses": [
7         "Hey :-)",
8         "Hello, thanks for visiting",
9         "Hi there, what can I do for you?",
10        "Hi there, how can I help?"
11      ]
12    },
13    {
14      "tag": "greet",
15      "patterns": [
16        "How are you?",
17        "How are you doing?",
18        "How do you do?",
19        "How are you feeling?",
20        "What up?",
21        "What's up?"
22      ],
23      "responses": [
24        "I'm fine, and you?",
25        "Not too bad, how about you?",
26        "I'm doing great, thanks for asking!",
27        "I'm chill... Got any questions for me?",
28        "I'm calm... Need any help?"
29      ]
30    },
31    {
32      "tag": "response",
33      "patterns": ["I'm fine", "I'm good.", "I'm alright"],
34      "responses": ["That's good to hear", "Nice to hear"]
35    }
36  ]
37 }
```

Figure 4.1: Preview of the JSON file containing user intents and bot's responses

Stemming words is a way to find their root. For example, the root of the word “chasing” would be “chas”, and for “happening” it would be “happen”. Stemming was used to generalize the meanings of sentences and to reduce the vocabulary of the model, which resulted in a shorter training time. This process also benefits the model's precision, as the words with the same stem will be treated the same. A snapshot of the stemming process is displayed in Figure 4.3.

With the data prepared, it created a bag of words. Machine learning algorithms work with numerical input, usually, it is an array with each element between 0.0 and 1.0. To feed the list of words to the model, there's a need for a way to represent it as a list of numbers. One such way is using a bag of words. The bag will represent each pattern as an array of 0 and 1. Each position in the array corresponds to the words from the stemmed list of supported words. For each element of the array, the value of 1 will mean that the word is present in the pattern, and the value of 0 will be used otherwise.

When using a bag of words, the order in which the words come in the sentence is lost. Sequence representation models such as convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks consider but have their disadvantages. Exploration of the implementation of such models is not in the scope of this work, but it might improve the results of the classifier. The bag of words implementation is presented in the code snippet shown in Figure 4.6.

With the bag of words prepared, the inputs and outputs of this model can be represented. For the implementation, a neural network with 4 layers will be used. The first layer is the input layer, the second and third ones are hidden layers, and the last layer is the output layer. The neural network will take user input represented as a bag or words and output the class that the input belongs to (i.e., the intent).

```
30
31 # stem and lower each word
32 ignore_words = ['?', '.', '!']
33 all_words = [stem(w) for w in all_words if w not in ignore_words]
34 # remove duplicates and sort
35 all_words = sorted(set(all_words))
36 tags = sorted(set(tags))
37
38 print(len(xy), "patterns")
39 print(len(tags), "tags:", tags)
40 print(len(all_words), "unique stemmed words:", all_words)
41
```

Figure 4.2: PyTorch model stemming the “bag of words”

```
PROBLEMS 51 OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL VISUALTEXT

(venv) C:\Users\ayool\Desktop\Project AIvy>python train.py
124 patterns
32 tags: ['asking', 'booking', 'continuation', 'delivery', 'eating', 'ending', 'funny', 'game',
'positive', 'presentation', 'project', 'response', 'rock', 'scissors', 'services', 'sexuality',
136 unique stemmed words: ["'d", "'m", "'s", ',', 'a', 'accept', 'actual', 'agent', 'alright', 'a
, 'bye', 'call', 'can', 'card', 'cash', 'choos', 'cool', 'credit', 'damn', 'day', 'design', 'dic
, 'get', 'give', 'good', 'goodby', 'have', 'hello', 'help', 'hey', 'hi', 'hour', 'how', 'human',
'mastercard', 'me', 'motherfuck', 'must', 'my', "n't", 'name', 'need', 'nice', 'no', 'not', 'now
'play', 'pleas', 'present', 'project', 'pussi', 'realli', 'redirect', 'rock', 'rout', 'sang', 'sa
e', 'thi', 'time', 'to', 'up', 'want', 'websit', 'were', 'what', 'when', 'who', 'with', 'work',
136 32
Epoch [100/1000], Loss: 0.3290
Epoch [200/1000], Loss: 0.0360
Epoch [300/1000], Loss: 0.0154
Epoch [400/1000], Loss: 0.0029
Epoch [500/1000], Loss: 0.0006
Epoch [600/1000], Loss: 0.0009
Epoch [700/1000], Loss: 0.0000
Epoch [800/1000], Loss: 0.0001
Epoch [900/1000], Loss: 0.0000
Epoch [1000/1000], Loss: 0.0000
final loss: 0.0000
training complete. file saved to data.pth

(venv) C:\Users\ayool\Desktop\Project AIvy>
```

Figure 4.3: Snapshot of the number of unique words at the end of stemming

```

17  xy = []
18  # Loop through each sentence in our intents patterns
19  for intent in intents['intents']:
20      tag = intent['tag']
21      # add to tag list
22      tags.append(tag)
23      for pattern in intent['patterns']:
24          # tokenize each word in the sentence
25          w = tokenize(pattern)
26          # add to our words list
27          all_words.extend(w)
28          # add to xy pair
29          xy.append((w, tag))
30
31  # stem and lower each word

```

Figure 4.4: Looping through each sentence of the intent's patterns

```

42 # create training data
43 x_train = []
44 y_train = []
45 for (pattern_sentence, tag) in xy:
46     # X: bag of words for each pattern_sentence
47     bag = bag_of_words(pattern_sentence, all_words)
48     x_train.append(bag)
49     # y: PyTorch CrossEntropyLoss needs only class labels, not one-hot
50     label = tags.index(tag)
51     y_train.append(label)
52
53 x_train = np.array(x_train)
54 y_train = np.array(y_train)
55

```

Figure 4.5: PyTorch populating the empty arrays with tokens and intents

As for the design decisions for this model, it uses the recommendations of Jeff Heaton as a guideline. This is found reasonable, as his recommendations are supported by a number of works in the field of neural networks. With the model prepared, training the model to use the data can begin. For this, it will use the method “range ()” and define the number of epochs as 100. This number represents the number of times the classifier will see the same data during the training process. Next, in the command line of the code editor VS Code, the command “python train.py” is run as demonstrated in Figure 4.3. Training large models can take a long time, but in this case, it took approximately 33 seconds. When the training is done, the model is saved for further use. This will allow importing the model instead of retraining it from scratch.

Now it populates these empty arrays with tokens and intents, as shown in the code snippet given in Figure 4.5.

With the training complete, it creates and calls a method that will use the model. This method will have to convert the user input into a bag of words. For convenience, it will be extracted as a separate method, which is presented in Figure 4.8.

To start the chat, in the command line, the command “python chat.py” is run as presented in the code snippet demonstrated in Figure 4.9.

With all the steps done, the implementation of the intent-based chatbot is complete. To use the bot, “python chat.py” is run to make sure everything works. The next step was to start adding contextuality to the bot, which is described in the next subsection.

```
train.py > [e] X_train
1  import numpy as np
2  import random
3  import json
4
5  import torch
6  import torch.nn as nn
7  from torch.utils.data import Dataset, DataLoader
8
9  from nltk_utils import bag_of_words, tokenize, stem
10 from model import NeuralNet
11
12 with open('intents.json', 'r') as f:
13     intents = json.load(f)
14
15 all_words = []
16 tags = []
17 xy = []
```

Figure 4.6: Implementation of the bag words

```

93
94 # Train the model
95 for epoch in range(num_epochs):
96     for (words, labels) in train_loader:
97         words = words.to(device)
98         labels = labels.to(dtype=torch.long).to(device)
99
100         # Forward pass
101         outputs = model(words)
102         # if y would be one-hot, we must apply
103         # labels = torch.max(labels, 1)[1]
104         loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
105
106         # Backward and optimize
107         optimizer.zero_grad()
108         loss.backward()
109         optimizer.step()
110
111     if (epoch+1) % 100 == 0:
112         print (f'Epoch [{epoch+1}/{num_epochs}], Loss: {loss.item():.4f}')
113

```

Figure 4.7: Training the model

4.5 Module for continual learning

In the current state, the chatbot can be used to make enquiries on the website. Without named entity recognition (NER), it is not able to generalize the inquiry, but the user can complete the inquiry. At this stage, it is ready to add an experimental module for continual learning. This work tries to achieve this functionality by implementing a method that retrains the model of the chatbot from the recognized user inputs as well as expands its dictionary. As this work uses a list of words limited to a few prompts added by the programmer, the initial dataset does not map most of the words to intents. This is exactly the job that is entrusted to the users. It is expected that the users inform the website owners using the message function on the website or contact the website owner on any of the social platforms provided.

```
50
51 if __name__ == "__main__":
52     print("Let's chat! (type 'quit' to exit)")
53     while True:
54         # sentence = "do you use credit cards?"
55         sentence = input("You: ")
56         if sentence == "quit":
57             break
58
59         resp = get_response(sentence)
60         print(resp)
61
```

Figure 4.8: Defining the method to call up the chat module

```
(venv) C:\Users\ayool\Desktop\Project AIvy>python chat.py
Let's chat! (type 'quit' to exit)
You: Hello
Hey :-)
You: How are you doing?
I'm doing great, thanks for asking!
You: █
```

Figure 4.9: Calling up the chat module in the command line

As the chatbot is used continually, the “intents.json” file will be updated regularly. This will further increase the bag of words and also help train the chatbot better. This will be done by adding more tags to the JSON file. Implementation of the module for continual learning is shown in the sample code snippet below.

```
{  
  "tag": "asking_tag",  
  "patterns": [  
    "What are you doing?",  
    "What are you up to?",  
    "What have you been up to?"  
  ],  
  "responses": [  
    "Nothing much... How about you?",  
    "Nothing really... Just here in my corner."  
  ]  
}
```

This method would be done when there is a compiled list of new intents, as it will be crucial to retrain the chatbot only on successfully recognized intents. The results, analysis and discussion of the implementation are presented in the following sections. In this case, the retraining process took below 1 second, but with larger datasets, this could take much longer. The training time can be reduced with better hardware, like, a CUDA-enabled graphics card.

4.6 Designing the web interface

After the model has been developed, the next step was to design a web interface to host the chatbot system. This step was crucial as to complete the thesis objective O2. To design the web interface, the three programming languages used were HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript.

First of all, the skeleton of the webpage was designed with the latest version of HyperText Markup Language (HTML5). Ordinary HTML syntax wasn't used as the interface was to be hosted using Flask. This required the HTML code to be written in Flask syntax as displayed in Figure 4.10. This process took about two hours as HTML is an easy language to work with.

A snapshot of the HTML code is presented in Figure 4.10 below.

After the skeleton of the web interface had been designed and all elements had been added using HTML, the latest version of Cascading Style Sheets (CSS3) was then used to add beautification to the interface. This involved adding theme colours, text colouring, adding background colours, and adding liveliness to the webpage. This process took between two and a half to three hours to complete, solely because of the amount of attentiveness that is required to use CSS. It requires a keen eye to design to pick and use the right colours, element spacing etc. Figure 4.11 below displays some of the CSS code used to design the web interface for the chat module.

Lastly, JavaScript was used to add interactivity to the web interface. This included also adding fetch APIs (Application Program Interface) that helped to get responses from the NLTK model that was previously designed. This was done to allow the seamless fetching of responses from the model without any crashes whatsoever. This process was time-consuming as it took almost five hours to finish up with the JavaScript code. Figure 4.12 shows a clear look at the JavaScript code used in designing the web interface

With these processes completed, the web interface had been designed. Snapshots of the web interface are presented in Figures 4.13 and 4.14.

The image shows a code editor window with the following HTML code:

```
1 <!DOCTYPE html>
2 <html Lang="en">
3   <head>
4     <meta charset="UTF-8" />
5     <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1.0" />
6     <title>Home</title>
7
8     <!-- font awesome cdn link -->
9     <link
10      rel="stylesheet"
11      href="https://cdn.jsdelivr.net/npm/font-awesome@5.15.2/css/all.min.css"
12    />
13
14     <!-- custom css file link -->
15
16     <link
17      rel="stylesheet"
18      href="{{ url_for('static', filename='style.css') }}"
19    />
20
21     <link
22      rel="stylesheet"
23      type="text/css"
24      href="{{ url_for('static', filename='chatstyle.css') }}"
25    />
26   </head>
27   <body>
28     <!-- header section starts -->
29
30     <header>
31       <h1 class="heading">Home</h1>
32
33       <div id="menu" class="fas fa-bars"></div>
34
35       <nav class="navbar">
36         <ul>
37           <li><a href="/home">Home</a></li>
38           <li><a href="/about">About Us</a></li>
39           <li><a href="/services">Our Services</a></li>
40           <li><a href="/contact">Contact Us</a></li>
41         </ul>
42     </body>
43 </html>
```

Figure 4.10: HTML is used to design the main interface of the web interface

The image shows a screenshot of the Visual Studio Code editor with a dark theme. The title bar at the top reads "style.css - Project Alvy - Visual Studio Code". The editor has several tabs open: "base.html", "app.py", "app.js", "style.css" (which is the active tab), "chatstyle.css", "home.html", and "chat.py". The "style.css" file is open, and the code is as follows:

```
static > # style.css > 1 @import url("https://fonts.googleapis.com/css2?family=Open+Sans:wght@300;400;600;700&display=swap");
2
3 :root {
4   --orange: #ca770b;
5 }
6
7 * {
8   font-family: "Open Sans", sans-serif;
9   margin: 0;
10  padding: 0;
11  box-sizing: border-box;
12  text-decoration: none;
13  outline: none;
14  border: none;
15  transition: all 0.2s linear;
16 }
17
18 *::selection {
19   background: var(--orange);
20   color: #fff;
21 }
22
23 html {
24   font-size: 62.5%;
25   overflow-x: hidden;
26 }
27
28 section {
29   padding: 0 7%;
30   padding-top: 12rem;
31 }
32
33 .btn {
34   font-size: 2rem;
35   padding: 0.7rem 3rem;
36   background: var(--orange);
37   color: #fff;
38   margin-top: 1rem;
39   cursor: pointer;
40 }
```

The code defines a root selector with a color variable, a universal selector for font and transition settings, a selection pseudo-class for highlighting, and specific styles for the html, section, and .btn elements. The interface includes a sidebar on the left with icons for Explorer, Search, Source Control, Run and Debug, Extensions, NLP, and a bottom status bar with icons for Run and Debug, Live Share, and Quokka.

Figure 4.11: An overview of the CSS code used in designing the web interlace

```
File Edit Selection View Go Run Terminal Help app.js - Project Alvy - Visual
base.html app.py JS app.js style.css chatstyle.css home.html
static > JS app.js > Chatbox > onSendButton > catch() callback
1 class Chatbox {
2   constructor() {
3     this.args = {
4       openButton: document.querySelector(".chatbox_button"),
5       chatBox: document.querySelector(".chatbox_support"),
6       sendButton: document.querySelector(".send_button"),
7     };
8
9     this.state = false;
10    this.messages = [];
11  }
12
13  display() {
14    const { openButton, chatBox, sendButton } = this.args;
15
16    openButton.addEventListener("click", () => this.toggleState(chatBox));
17
18    sendButton.addEventListener("click", () => this.onSendButton(chatBox));
19
20    const node = chatBox.querySelector("input");
21    node.addEventListener("keyup", ({ key }) => {
22      if (key === "Enter") {
23        this.onSendButton(chatBox);
24      }
25    });
26  }
27
28  toggleState(chatbox) {
29    this.state = !this.state;
30
31    // show or hides the box
32    if (this.state) {
33      chatbox.classList.add("chatbox--active");
34    } else {
35      chatbox.classList.remove("chatbox--active");
36    }
37  }
38
39  onSendButton(chatbox) {
40    var textField = chatbox.querySelector("input");
```

Figure 2.12: Demonstration of the JavaScript code used in designing the web interface

Figure 4.13: Landing page of the chat module

Figure 4.14: The chat module in use

4.7 Results

This section presents the results of the case study chatbot developed in the previous section. It started by demonstrating the work of this case study chatbot (discussed in the previous section) and validating it with the small corpus. When running the chatbot, the results with and without continual learning enabled are collected for later comparison. In the case of this case study chatbot implementation, the program was run for a number of conversations and its results were recorded, mapping each conversation and the inputs within it to the probability that the chatbot got when assigning the input to some intent. The same process is then repeated while using the retraining method and recording the results with continual learning for the same conversations.

All these results were analysed using a questionnaire designed using Google Forms. Figure 4.15 displays a snapshot of the questionnaire. This questionnaire was filled out by 70 respondents. After the questionnaires were filled, a pie chart was drafted that calculates the percentage of individuals opinions of the bot's responses. These are demonstrated in Figures 4.16, 4.17 and Figure 4.18.

The analysis and discussion of the results will follow in the next section.

Chatbot Performance Evaluation Form

This form is to help gather information that helps evaluate the performance of web-based chatbot designed for a final year project.

ayoelaemmanuel083@gmail.com [Switch account](#)

* Indicates required question

Email *

Your email

What was your input? *

Your answer

What was the bot's response? *

Your answer

What response did you expect to get? *

Your answer

Response Speed *

	Very fast	Fast	Slow	Very slow
.	☐	☐	☐	☐

Response Relevance *

	Very relevant	Relevant	Irrelevant	Very irrelevant
.	☐	☐	☐	☐

User Satisfaction *

	Very satisfied	Satisfied	Unsatisfied	Very unsatisfied
.	☐	☐	☐	☐

Overall Precision Assessment *

	Very functional	Functional	Unfunctional	Very unfunctional
.	☐	☐	☐	☐

Any Feedback or comments?

Your answer

Figure 4.15: The questionnaire used to determine the system's efficiency.

Count of Response Relevance

Figure 4.16: Pie chart displaying the relevance of the bot's responses

Count of Response Relevance

Figure 4.17: Pie chart displaying the speed of the bot's responses

Count of Response Relevance

Figure 4.18: Pie chart displaying the satisfaction of the users

4.8 Analysis of Results

- i. The system was deemed very valuable to website users of various levels as they found the chatbot system very informative and useful. Website users got access to valuable information with ease.
- ii. Website users could easily ask questions and get answers instantly saving a lot of time or research and contacting remote staff.
- iii. A very minuscule amount of people had little to no experience with using chatbots to get responses to their queries. Most users reveal their previous experience with using chatbots to generate answers to several complex questions. Examples: ChatGPT, Poe, Snapchat AI, Ask Your Telegram AI etc.
- iv. A huge percentage of the chatbot's users claim to have gotten a good response from the bot. This also applies to their previous experience with chatbots.
- v. The general community with interest in the test website found it useful given that they had queries or questions on accessing services from the website. The web system is deemed very useful not only to the website's users but rather to a lot of web visitors.
- vi. The chatbot could only appropriately respond to user intents, based on what it was previously trained with.

4.9 Cost/Time Analysis

The design and implementation of the chatbot system took between two and three weeks. The first stage was to design the system architecture and user interface before programming the actual chat module. Designing the system user interface would take approximately three to four days. Web programming for both the backend and frontend using Python's Flask and HTML (HyperText Markup Language) would take a full week to ensure the system doesn't crash or malfunction at any point. PyTorch modelling would be combined with the collection of data (questions and relative answers). The collection of data and modelling of an Artificial

Intelligence model would take between three to four days as adjustments would be made to produce a model of great accuracy.

Finally, the web programming of a land-on page took one day, since the model was developed simply using HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript on Visual Studio Code. The best thing about software projects is that they're scalable and cost-efficient since most services are cloud-based. The costs amounted to NGN 0.00. Render's free hosting service was used as well as its free domain name. This resulted in the absence of any fees towards hosting or purchasing a domain name.

4.10 Project Limitations

This implementation of the chatbot does not include a module for named entity recognition, which would be beneficial for this type of chatbot but is not necessary for testing the implementation of the continual learning concept. Another limitation is the lack of support for the recognition of multiple intents and multiple contexts from a single user input. Sometimes user inputs can carry multiple intents, and there are several ways to deal with this issue, but this was left outside of the scope of this project. One more limitation is the number of chatbot types used to test continual learning. In this work, the testing will be carried out with the developed chatbot. Increasing the dataset will be a regular process as a result of the kind of chatbot developed in this project. As for the larger dataset, it has to be generated continually, it contains non-contextual data and its results represent a different perspective of continual learning than this question-answering dataset. This concludes this section of chatbot implementation, result gathering and analysis, which completes the thesis objectives O2, O3 and O4 specified in the Introduction section.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Discussion

The final system performed as expected and the results obtained were as expected since such a bot is a first of its kind in the development of websites and customer service. Technology is moving at a very fast pace and many industries are now heaving being data-driven. Implementing technology on all fronts of web development allows the industry to benefit from several innovations. Utilizing web technology serves a great purpose for website owners that might not have adequate equipment to utilize available services. Developing this web-based chatbot system enables ease to access of information in simple steps. Several industries namely health, E-commerce and even humanities are implementing virtual assistants in the space of actual humans. This has to some extent faced criticism due to the prospect that people might end up losing employment due to Artificial Intelligence. Creating this chatbot seems to help a lot of people on the web not only business owners. Future developments are to be made, and further enhancements are to be implemented to ensure that the technology develops coherently with the underlying changes in the fields mentioned.

With the analysis complete, it can be concluded that the method of continual learning can be applied to expand a dataset for a chatbot implementation task. For real-world chatbots, continual learning makes sense when user inputs are supervised by a human or a trusted algorithm to ensure that the classifier learns correctly. Alternatively, the probability limit could be set to a sufficiently high value, so that the learning takes place only with the most probable inputs. This will decrease the effectiveness of continual learning, but at the same time safeguard the classifier against incorrect learning to a certain extent. From the analysis, it can also be concluded that it would be a good idea to only use important words in input to train the classifier.

5.2 Recommendations

Artificial Intelligence can be applied in many fields of web development. Technology as a whole can be applied on many fronts to improve day-to-day operations. Voice-enabled chatbots will enable ease of use for the general person. Chatbot agents that can be altered to fit a particular language should be developed to cater to people in different areas of the world. As observed, most website users do not use English on a day-to-day basis but rather their native languages. This comes as a limitation since operating some technological gadgets requires an extensive understanding of modern English. Several technologies can be implemented in web development to improve transparency and accessibility. Blockchain can also be used to utilize supply networks and Virtual Reality can be used for 3D modelling and assessment of various kinds. The list is endless as technology is developing every day.

5.3 Conclusion

One of the technologies that have been making the most noise in the world of technology is Artificial Intelligence. AI ecosystem is vast with only a small part of it being explored today. Large businesses have shown interest in applying AI in different parts of their infrastructure to increase profit. When they start to explore their possibilities with AI, it becomes clear that it has many different applications. From this comes the understanding that not every area of AI is equally developed. While some areas have several polished tools that can be directly applied to business, other areas are not completely explored and the best-developed tools turn out to be prototypes.

As of today, Artificial Intelligence is perhaps the most interesting as well as challenging field of research today. It has already proven itself for solving some major problems for mankind. In the near future, Artificial Intelligence will present itself on a larger canvas and will become integrated into the day-to-day lifestyle of individuals. Using a chatbot to provide quick answers to daily active web users has shown the potential of how Artificial Intelligence can

impact lives in the future. Auto responses and general automation will change customer care service in the future. This will further enhance human operations and reduce human errors that usually lead to day-to-day incidences.

This work proposes the application of the continual learning method to chatbots. Although the results are clear for intent-based contextual chatbots, they are not sufficient to justify the use of this method in all possible scenarios. Thus, there is still work to be done to improve the method itself as well as the chatbot used to test it for further scenarios, which are closer to various real-world applications. One of the improvements to the method is introducing an algorithm that could ensure that the chatbot improves with every iteration of continual learning. Every user input can be used to retrain the chatbot, but not all of them will make a positive impact on its precision. Choosing the right inputs to use for training is one of the keys to making continual learning useful in real-world applications. In the case of larger datasets, another improvement would be to speed up the process of retraining the classifier. The process took just a few seconds on a small dataset but might take up to a minute on larger ones.

Next, there is a description of what else can be done to improve this solution or any other implementation to facilitate the application of this method to other problems. Continual learning has the potential for synergy with different types of contexts, but in this work, it was only tested with a single way of implementing the lingual context. Apart from other lingual context implementations, other contexts such as situational, persistence and emotional could be applied. Additionally, the implementation in this work used the “bag of words” method to create inputs for the classifier, and it is believed that its precision could be improved by using sequence representation models such as convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks.

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